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Deliverable 6.3: **Community of Practice and Training Activities Plan**

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Abstract

This report details the training activities and community-engagement activities of GraspOS, describing the background, purpose, and processes in place to ensure fruitful engagements with various stakeholders from various organisations that are interested in ‘open science-aware responsible research assessment practices’.

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Abbreviation List

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment	CoARA
Community of Practice	CoP
Open Science Assessment Framework	OSAF
Research Funding Organisation	RFO
Research Performing Organisation	RPO
Responsible Research Assessment	RRA
Leiden University (CWTS)	ULEI
Work Package	WP

1. Executive Summary

As part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy of GraspOS, we will engage stakeholders through two key WP6 activities, namely a 'Community of Practice' (CoP) and Training. The CoP revolves around the core question of how research assessment considers open science in various settings. The aim is to create a selection of examples, where the goal is not to streamline these open science aware assessment practices by defining how open science is to be considered in assessment practice, but to add layers of interpretation about the forms of assessment that the onset of open science enables and vice versa. The CoP will be designed, facilitated and evaluated in a co-creative fashion, which is detailed in the description below and will kick-off in October 2023 after a three month-long promotion through different media. On the other hand, training will be developed to complement the CoP as well as provide a standalone solution to address the challenges that stakeholders will face in integrating open science and responsible research assessment, which will take a co-creation approach to involve a diverse set of stakeholders.

2. Introduction

In the context of GraspOS, WP6 represents the work plan for both outward and inward communication and dissemination activities that aim at supporting and maximising the expected impacts as detailed in Section 2 of the grant agreement¹. The strategic aims of the project are diverse, but orient themselves along the idea that **research funding organisations, research performing organisations, and other research-related entities need to be enabled to consider open science in their assessment praxis** through both the technical affordances surrounding their research assessment activities and the social and organisational context in which these assessments take place. As a WP that is aimed at supporting and maximising these strategic aims, it becomes important to define *how* this is to be achieved.

The key deliverable to consider this question is the D6.1 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan", which is submitted simultaneously with this deliverable. We are mentioning this because it is important to understand the Community of Practice and the Training Activities - which are the key concern of this plan - not as two disjointed activities, but as strategic leverages for maximising the project's impacts. Nonetheless, the planning for each activity will be described separately from each other to recognise the different issues that need to be considered in designing, implementing and evaluating each activity. This plan thus outlines two activities:

¹ See Grant Agreement, p. 24

- (1) T6.2 (ULEI): Identifying, creating and engaging a “Community of Practice” (hereafter called *CoP*) that is to contribute to the development and testing of, and learning about ‘open science aware responsible research assessment’.
- (2) T6.3 (OPENAIRE): Providing the training that is necessary to empower the relevant stakeholders to undertake the concepts of open science and responsible research assessment.

Finally, each activity is described in a dedicated section of this document, in which the background, ambitions, planning, implementation and evaluation are described.

3. Community of Practice facilitated by GraspOS

First of all, we would like to extend the idea of what this CoP can become for GraspOS. In the grant agreement, the CoP is envisioned and described as an instrument to allow GraspOS to “co-design its plans with a broader community of practice by creating spaces to connect people, promote mutual learning with the selected pilots, [and] foster collaboration practices” (p.19). Whilst this sentence encapsulates to some degree the core ideas, we would like to extend this notion of the CoP by leaning on a description by a publication from the Joint Research Centre², which was produced as an output from an evaluation of the multiple communities affiliated to the European Commission in 2018 and another research into these observations and existing communities in 2020 and 2021.

The authors stress an important factor that has not been made explicit in the grant agreement. That is, on the one hand, if facilitated well, a CoP speaks to both the tacit and explicit knowledge of the participants and provides a space for making these knowledges workable, transferable and thereby creating a **space for mutual learning**. On the other hand, it explicitly focuses on fields of practice and thereby makes sure to **appreciate divergent perspectives and assessment realities** as their differences appear. Although this will reappear in the higher-level objectives of this CoP, this point can already be captured as a principle for the activities described here: **the goal is to learn from heterogeneous assessment practices** that consider open science rather than trying to streamline them in a modus of implementation. As such, the goal of the Community of Practice is not to define, but

² European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2021). The communities of practice playbook: a playbook to collectively run and develop communities of practice: print friendly version. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/37048>

rather expand our interpretations of the various forms that open science in the context of research assessment can take in practice.

This section is divided into various sub-sections that first consider the status quo (including the descriptions in the grant agreement), a description of the considerations that the GraspOS team has had with regards to the CoP and finally a description of the current plan for launching the CoP in early fall 2023 and how we, the team involved in activities of WP6, and in particular ULEI, are planning on doing that.

Purpose

Before formulating a vision for the GraspOS CoP, we want to rehearse the challenges that bring this community to life in the first place. Of course, these are directly linked to the very challenges that the GraspOS project cares for and tries to address. GraspOS departs from the insight that there are multiple movements at the moment that address similar interlinked issues in research and innovation in Europe. There are **two wider movements which the project considers. One is** a European, but also national and organisational **agenda to advance open science in Europe**, which is visible in multiple policy contexts on various scales³. **Another** major movement are the commitments that many organisations make to advancing responsible research assessment⁴. Launched in 2022, the **Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment** (CoARA) has managed to get support from a wide range of organisations in Europe, including research institutions, research funders, and societal stakeholders, for an agreement on reforming research assessment praxis towards more responsible ends. Open science translates in this agreement as an ideal to handle and process data in transparent ways and to be collaborative, but is otherwise not really discussed, despite direct relations between e.g. indicators for research assessment and e.g. the affordances of open research information infrastructures or the access to knowledge that directly enables or disables particular assessments to happen. The GraspOS CoP aims to ensure that this interrelation gets sufficient attention. As such, we formulate the central question for this CoP as follows:

How can responsible research assessment consider open science and vice versa?

This central question connects both movements with each other and provides the **conversational space** to enquire into the differences between them, similarities and challenges that both face in order to shape better knowledge for the future. Furthermore, it puts forward a value proposition for each movement and attached organisations by allowing

³ See e.g. https://www.openscience.nl/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/NPOS_AmbitionDocument.pdf

⁴ See <https://coara.eu/>

them to transcend and learn from the other, with an implicit urge to respond to the risk of both movements developing apart from each other. From this challenge, we will now formulate a shared vision for the CoP.

Shared vision and strategy

Departing from the question formulated above, this vision serves as a pointer for what kind of interactions we hope to be fostering. A community of practice is not as loose as a network and some degree of commitment is necessary. As such, the vision - that is still up to negotiation in collaboration with the participants when this activity kicks off in late Q3 2023 - acts as a long term orientation. To approximate it, we want to appropriate two questions that were put forward in the CoP Playbook by the Joint Research Centre:

1. What do we aspire to achieve? and
2. What is our long-term goal?

These will underlie the first encounters between the various actors. As the report describes:

“When people are aligned around a shared vision, they understand where the community is going, how it will foster the development of its members, the organisation and other stakeholders, and what it will take to succeed. They understand how their work serves the bigger picture—the organisation’s success—and they feel that they are at the centre of things, making a significant contribution.” (European Commission 2021, p.31).

Formulating such an underlying shared *challenge* and *vision* differentiates a loose network from a community of practice and will be first order when having the first collective encounters. Of course, formulating a shared vision depends largely on the grounds upon which the collective becomes a collective in the first place. Evidently, it depends on the **positioning** that the GraspOS CoP will assume, which is directly linked to strategic considerations that we have conceptualised, but are yet unsure of which to follow due to this very formative stage of the project on the one hand, and external organisations on the other. However, to summarise, our conversations with various internal and peripheral actors of GraspOS have yielded two main lines of strategy for the CoP, which focus on the signatories of CoARA as key audience and mobilising them differently. This is due to at least two reasons. First, as an EOSC-funded project, focusing on the community around CoARA sets an expectation that GraspOS tries to translate not only between EOSC and CoARA, but also two dominant focal areas of Open Science. That is, one focusing on the technical infrastructure on the one hand and the other on ‘responsible research assessment’ dimensions of open science. The two strategies are as follows:

One strategy is to formalise a partnership with CoARA through which GraspOS, and in particular the Community of Practice of GraspOS, can be positioned as a space that provides value to the signatories of CoARA in the form of guidance and knowledge to formulating a plan of implementation - a formal requirement by CoARA for any member organisation. This process has started in the form of GraspOS partners teaming up and having proposed a CoARA Working Group, submitted in May 2023, with their respective organisations. The status of this application is still open at the time of writing, which is why an alternative strategy has been conceived that is unaffected by uncertainties.

The second (and alternative) strategy holds fast to the already-existing collaborations and existing thought that has happened as part of the preparations for the CoP. The strategy is to hold on to the description (and agreement) by the organisations that GraspOS has submitted a CoARA Working Group proposal with and host these initial organisations as the Community of Practice, providing the conversational space and agency necessary to appreciate the working group proposal independently from CoARA. As such, the contents are very aligned with both the first strategy and GraspOS, however the communication and the messaging to engage the audiences require a different approach - possibly at the expense of a stronger value proposition due to the endorsement and formal relationship to CoARA.

Identification and Enrolling Participants

Key to a community of practice is the community on the one hand and the practice on the other. **Actors thus must navigate settings in which the thinking is shaped by and through practice.** For the themes that are addressed through the project and the planned activities, the range of relevant actors is rather diverse, as described in the grant agreement. They largely represent the actors and networks to which the partners in GraspOS have access to. These include:

- Research performing and funding organisations who are implementing research assessment agendas or have signed CoARA; e.g. DG-RTD, European Universities (Erasmus+), MSCA, Universities Research Alliances and the OPUS Consortium (UEFDSI)
- Providers of data/metrics infrastructure and representatives of local and national monitoring infrastructures (e.g. OpenAIRE Working Group on National OS Policy Monitoring); and representatives from Research Infrastructures (e.g. OpenAIRE, OPERAS, EGI and EOSC Association members)
- Representatives from national open science initiatives and bodies (e.g. members of CoNOSC via TSV and the National Reference Points for open access network via OpenAIRE, who may also be a direct conduit to ERA groups).

- Representatives from scholarly societies and other professional bodies who seek to explore domain discipline practices and solutions for their constituencies (e.g. CS/AI interested parties are Informatics Europe, ERCIM or ACM Europe, TSV in Finland)
- Researchers who focus on monitoring and evaluation of European research and innovation (e.g. Super MoRRI, a network of SwafS-related projects, etc.)

By and large, GraspOS is composed of these actor groups that all, in diverse ways, relate to open science and research assessment. The nine pilots that GraspOS leads, including RFOs, RPOs and thematic pilots across Europe, are not exempt from this and represent a considerable and important actor group that will be given a prominent role in the CoP, namely in the form of 'champions' - that is, key representatives that share their experiences and act as a first empirical matter for the CoP to learn from and grow.

Whilst all of the actor types that are listed are crucial to the development of open science, we - as partners in WP6 - have decided to focus largely on two main groups. That is, representatives from **research performing** and representatives from **research funding organisations**. This is for at least four reasons. For one, all of the nine pilots either directly fall under one of these two categories or indirectly target organisations in these categories. Secondly, these categories allow for focusing the communications along these two key actor groups in the research system. Thirdly, research performing and research funding *organisations* may include e.g. professional bodies, initiatives that drive certain transitions or research information representatives (monitoring, data provision etc.). Finally, and given that we focus on *practice*, we want to involve mainly these actor groups that indeed *practice* research(er) assessment or are affected by it, which largely spans these two categories of actors, too. This narrows our audience to:

1. GraspOS pilot representatives (both RPOs and RFOs)
2. Actors identifying as representatives of RFOs, irrespective of their position
3. Actors identifying as representatives of RPOs, irrespective of their position

Of course, the base assumption is that these actors *participate* to certain extents rather than passively 'listen in'. While that is of course okay, all participants will eventually be asked to contribute in one form or another.

IDENTIFICATION OF ACTOR GROUPS

The grant agreement already spelled out one of the approaches with which relevant actor groups are identified, **namely the mobilisation of professional networks and initiatives in which many of the consortium members of GraspOS** are involved. These initiatives include, but are not limited to, GraspOS' relations to European Universities (Erasmus+),

CoNOSC, Super MoRRI, NRPs, OpenAIRE and Operas networks, OPUS (WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-45), PathOS (WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-40) and CoARA.

A second approach with which relevant actors are planned to be identified **involves the use of Twitter**. Although access to the Twitter data got restricted quite heavily, ULEI maintains a database for scientometric analysis, which includes information on Twitter users who have at least once shared a scientific article. This database will be used to search for individuals, initiatives or organisations that relate to both open science and research assessment by searching for a co-occurrence of respective words in users' descriptions⁵.

These two moves allow us to identify a range of potentially relevant actors. Following the identification of potentially interested actors, the next step is to make sure they:

1. Know what the GraspOS CoP is about and what value proposition this poses to them and
2. Ensure a mechanism that allows interested actors to sign up / signal their interest.

PROMOTION AND PARTICIPATION

After the relevant actors have been identified and listed, we will reach out to them through GraspOS members, who will be asked to spread the word (and a pre-written invitation) during the monthly WP6 meeting in July 2023 and a follow-up email. Additionally, the identified Twitter users will be contacted by using the messaging function of Twitter via the GraspOS account. This message / email will detail:

- Introduction to GraspOS
- Purpose of GraspOS CoP
- Format
- Commitment and a
- URL

The URL will link to a dedicated GraspOS CoP webpage on graspOS.eu - the official website of the project. On that site, visitors are presented with a more detailed version of the information in the message and a textbox, in which they may sign up by submitting the email address they wish to be contacted on⁶. This will allow actors to sign up not only voluntarily, but also in an informed manner.

⁵ A multitude of search strings was used to include peripheral wordings / formulations of those terms.

⁶ Name(s), title, organisation and other personal information will not be collected, as the email address is the only piece of information that is needed at that point. GDPR will be respected and data will be handled / processed as described.

The email addresses will be collected in accordance with the data management protocols of the GraspOS project. The sole purpose of the email addresses is to contact the actors that are interested in order to inform them of the details regarding the meetings of the GraspOS CoP.

The mechanism as described above ensures that, despite the fact that potential audiences are contacted via personal or professional networks or beyond these networks through Twitter, participation is voluntary, deliberate and transparent. This process of promotion and registration will run from June 2023 through September 2023.

Time, Place and Format

PRE-KICKOFF

Due to the formative stages of the pilots and the project, the uncertainties around the CoARA working group, as well as the summer where potential audiences might be travelling - we decided to kick off in October 2023 and proceed in a bimonthly fashion. The summer months (June, July and August) will be used to consolidate the planning and choices made, like in this deliverable, set up the webpage and contact gathering mechanisms as described above and promote the Community of Practice; building a list of interested participants.

In terms of place, and based upon the consideration of the various places that potentially relevant audiences are located at, it is almost implied that we will (need to) make use of virtual formats that ULEI will facilitate. Immediate thoughts relate to virtual meeting rooms like Zoom or Microsoft Teams, but we want to keep open additional, supplementary digital platforms and services that may be used to foster a sense of interaction between the participants.

Once participants have signed up, they will be contacted in the beginning of September with a Save-The-Date for the second week of October, namely the Wednesday, 18.10.2023 from 10:00 to 11:30 CEST. The first week of October will be used to send the dial-in details to the contact-list. Finally, the first session will mainly revolve around setting up:

1. a shared question (departing from the purpose as described above)
2. a shared vision (objectives of the group, such as a 'manifesto', or other outputs)

Taking co-creative principles at heart, these two first goals will be negotiated with the participants, balancing what they value and the requirements by GraspOS. In the grant agreement, the CoP is described as follows:

“The CoP integrates diverse groups of actors to be involved in the design, development, testing and validation of the OS infrastructure, including the pilot owners who will act as champions within their communities, sharing experiences, practices with the larger CoP.”⁷

Whilst this description puts the GraspOS needs first (involve participants in the design, development, testing and validation of technical assets produced by GraspOS), we want, with the first session(s), to create, formulate and agree on a *common* purpose as described in the first subsection of this document.

POST-KICKOFF

The recurring process surrounding the meetings, which will take place in a bimonthly fashion, will be organised as follows:

- (1) After each meeting, a one-page document is written that describes the key points, learnings and happenings during the meeting.
- (2) This description will be used to discuss, during the ULEI biweekly GraspOS meetings, the focus of the next session.
- (3) Two weeks before the following meeting of the CoP, this theme will be circulated in a small abstract in a shared GoogleDoc(ument). This will allow all participants of the CoP to not only see, but also edit or comment on the abstract that will structure the following meeting.
- (4) On the day of the event, and based on an agenda that outlines the abstract's contents, ULEI will moderate the session.
- (5) After the event, and depending on the outcomes, the one-pager will be written to capture the actions, learnings etc. that will be used in the following step (1) again.

This organisation of the workflow around the CoP is based on previous experiences from periodic events that were organised by ULEI. Because this deliverable is due much earlier than we will have substantial knowledge of the participant's wants and needs, this description is purposefully describing the procedural dimensions of this activity. All of these suggested processes may be subject to change, if new knowledge gears the WP6 members and CoP participants towards different decisions that can be considered as more useful or better for the collective that this activity addresses.

Engaging and Building the Community of Practice

⁷ GraspOS Grant Agreement, p.12

With the background purpose of the CoP by GraspOS, the process until the kick-off and the recurring process after the kick-off in place, we can now turn our gaze towards the type of community we want to build and what principles we can formulate to guide our actions.

As already alluded to in the last section, we will build engagement by orienting ourselves to principles surrounding participatory ideas of creation. Such 'co-creative' principles are also the reason why this document cannot yet speak of content-related matters. That is, because it presupposes a flat hierarchy in this community, where responsibilities, structures, contents and purpose should be largely decided upon *collectively*. This builds not only engagement with the participants, but also a sense of co-responsibility for and co-ownership of this community.

There are three rough demands for establishing the collective ground on which the community can rest. These are inspired by recommendations from a report on communities of practice, as alluded to earlier in the first section of the document⁸. These include:

1. Community membership and stakeholder mapping
2. Governance and
3. Establishing a risk-free environment

Below, we will describe each in more detail and finally conclude with a number of guiding principles that should be regarded as core values for the building of this community⁹.

COMMUNITY MEMBERSHIP AND STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

This builds on the previous activity of identifying and promoting registration for the CoP. In particular, having established a list of potential actors does not grant us insight into the skills, knowledge, stakes, interests, alliances and networks they bring to the community. Stakeholder mapping can help identify these and make known to others who one is, what one brings, what one wants and why. The first step is thus to map the participants (i.e. facilitate a session where a collective mapping exercise is performed). This will allow clustering of the actors in organic, community-driven categories (for instance based on potential involvement, interests or alliances, level of interest in the topic, etc.). With this knowledge in mind, one can start thinking about different types of memberships and define them, if necessary. This includes e.g. drawing a boundary between "a core group" and an "extended group" that comes with different responsibilities / levels of participation, which connects to the next point.

GOVERNANCE

⁸ European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2021). The communities of practice playbook: a playbook to collectively run and develop communities of practice: print friendly version. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/37048>

⁹ This includes any interaction, in-person, textual, virtual, direct or indirect.

After having made known who the community is, we need to establish how the community will work together, take decisions and act on them. The goal here is to allow for participation and the sharing of responsibility. Decisions need to be made openly and fairly, in a transparent and collective way. This can take different forms and manifest itself in e.g. community participation guidelines, codes of conduct, etc. What form of governance will be used will be paid particular attention to in the first encounters and handled with care, in order to ensure the next point.

ESTABLISHING A RISK-FREE ENVIRONMENT

A community of practice has been described as a “hierarchy-free learning zone”¹⁰, which we think fits our vision of the GraspOS community. ULEI will act as community moderators / managers, and will ensure to build a risk-free environment, including the recognition that e.g. different people relate to open science and research assessment differently, which is why any question is a legitimate question, even if it might be perceived as ‘naive’ by the person who wants to ask something; that there are different forms of knowledge that should all be respected. The whole point is to create an environment where people feel safe and open to speak up. This has direct relations to how the sessions will be facilitated, e.g. how people may / may not introduce themselves, the tone of voice during the meetings and communications, making sure that the most silent voice in the room gets to speak up, rather than having only dominant voices lead the conversation etc. - this will be handled carefully by the ULEI team.

DISCLOSURE

Given the dynamics of creative processes, such as GraspOS, plans may change. This also applies to what is said in this report. For the moment (May 2023), this report represents the state of play of the CoP, for which responsibility is taken by ULEI.

4. Training Plan

Training activities are aimed at educating stakeholders on the use of indicators, tools, services and infrastructure to further assist their use in the context of implementing OS-aware RRA approaches. A training course will be co-developed with the technology and infrastructure providers and hosted on the platform www.openplato.eu, a complete learning platform offered by OpenAIRE for organising all the activities, as well as on other similar platforms that may be available (e.g. via EOSC). We will aim for the delivery of 7 training events (either

¹⁰ European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2021). The communities of practice playbook: a playbook to collectively run and develop communities of practice: print friendly version. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2760/37048>

physical workshops/conferences or webinars) on the topics of the Open Metrics Infrastructure.

Overview

OBJECTIVES

The purpose of the training to be developed is to present and promote OSAF and how this tool can be used by various stakeholders: to promote the use of open RA dataspace; to present the advantages of its use and how the various data sources, methods, tools and services can be optimally exploited. Moreover, the aim will be to train the relevant stakeholders and partners on how to construct their indicators and metrics that include OS, as well as how to understand and use the respective activities and tools according to RRA policies. Of key importance is to promote the tools delivered by GraspOS such as OSAR, OS Monitor for Institutions and RFOs, AI-driven metadata enrichment tools and services and their evaluation through continuous feedback with participants. The overall purpose of the training process is to raise awareness and educate stakeholders about the OS indicator toolboxes and services that are being produced.

1. ONE COURSE ON OSAF IN OPENPLATO

Following the work in WP2 with a landscape analysis and the subsequent tasks on the OSAF and tools and services for the OSAF, training will run in parallel alongside these bringing in the pilots and CoP to help co-create a course about the OSAF and how it can be used by stakeholders. This will consist of defining those stakeholders and learning paths that will provide tailored content based on the desired outcome. OpenPlato and EOSC Future have already defined some learning paths which can be seen [here](#), but these will be revisited and added to based on the requirements that are revealed through the lifetime of GraspOS. WPs 3-5 will also be crucial to the training objectives, especially for the pilots in WP5.

Briefly, the methodology will follow established protocols already used elsewhere such as OpenPlato and EOSC Future: (1) a set of learning outcomes will be defined; (2) a template for designing training and learning resources will be used to define the training format (e.g. learning outcomes, mode of delivery, target stakeholder, duration, etc); (3) use a template to build a master document in which the content will be laid out, from text, to images and multimedia, and this will be done in concert with the relevant stakeholders and pilots; (4) delivery of the content in (3) via synchronous or asynchronous methods. For synchronous, these could be in-person or virtual live workshops, while for asynchronous, this will consist of

content created for self-paced learning on OpenPlato. The methodology described above will be reused wherever possible including the tutorials described below.

In the initial phases, pilots will be asked to bring examples that can be used to build content and will be involved throughout the process in the actual implementation and eventual reviewing prior to publication on OpenPlato or delivery through synchronous training. Assessments will also play a key role in the overall user experience, as described further below.

2. SEVEN TUTORIALS

These will be developed to educate the pilot participants and the external stakeholders on the benefits of adopting the new OSAF and on how to use the services and the infrastructure developed by WP3 and WP4 (each recorded 5-10 minutes on YouTube using OpenAIRE's channels).

- (1) OS Profile - what to include, how to build (for institutions, funders, RRA experts, policy makers, research admins).
- (2) OSAR - How to use, and register your protocol (for institutions, funders, RRA experts, policy makers, research admins).
- (3) GraspOS Dataspace for users - Understanding and using GraspOS dataspace (for institutions, funders, RRA experts, policy makers, research admins).
- (4) GraspOS AI enabled services for enrichment of research outputs - How to use these services of research outputs with missing attributes, novel metrics and missing semantics of existing research output links (for RRA Experts, providers).
- (5) GraspOS Dataspace for providers - How to share data/tools/methods/services for RRA. Interoperability. Access policies. Legal/ethical issues. (service providers).
- (6) OS Researcher Dashboard - How to use and build the dashboard in compliance to OS practices (for researchers).

Institutional OS Monitor - How to use and build a dashboard to include OS-aware indicators for RRA at organisational level (for institutions, funders).

Table 2.1 provides further detail with respect to the target audiences.

Table 2.1

Who	Learning outcomes	How
RRA experts Policy makers	Understand how to build indicators and metrics that include OS (results and practices).	Topic: OSAF Self-paced course (moodle) 3 x Webinars
Institutions (RPOs and RFOs)	Understand the facets of OS, e.g., coverage of different results and practices, methods. Evaluate and learn from examples of using dataspace (tools, indicators, metrics) to perform OS-aware RRA. Understand and use the OSAR service.	Topic: OS Profile Tutorial 4 x Webinars (1 for each domain pilot, 1 generic) Topic: GraspOS dataspace to access indicators/metrics Tutorial 2 x webinars Topic: OSAR 1 x Tutorial 2 x Webinars Topic: Institutional OS Monitor 1 x Tutorial 4 x Webinars (2 for funders, 2 for institutions)
Service Providers	Understand how to get involved and share data/methods/tools Understand how to use and disseminate services and tools according to RRA	Topic: Contributing to the GraspOS dataspace Tutorial 3 x Webinars
Researchers	Understand OS needs and how to shape/customise the individual's profile	Topic: OS Researcher Profile Tutorial 3 x Webinars

3. WEBINARS

These will be scheduled from Q2 of 2024 through to M32 at regular intervals and will be organised with a collaborative approach including the CoP, pilots and other stakeholders such as CoARA. Moreover, the OpenAIRE NOADs network will be leveraged to provide another level in which webinars can be scheduled and provide content.

4. CURRENTLY IDENTIFIED SYNCHRONOUS WORKSHOPS/TRAINING EVENTS TO BE TARGETED

CoARA meetings.

Ask partners for possible meetings.

OSFAIR 25.

National/institutional pilots are going to have to deliver physical training events.

Training Assessment

Providing assessments through the duration of a training is important to test the learner's receptiveness to the training being given, which in itself can be a good indicator of the quality of the training. Assessments will be given through e.g. quizzes at regular intervals wherever possible and especially in self-paced learning resources which are hosted on OpenPlato. Moodle allows for easy assessment of individuals and providing grades, feedback and ultimately badges which the learner can share with others to show that they have successfully completed a course. As part of this task, the WP6 team will also design a new badge to be awarded to successful learners to be used on OpenPlato.

As well as feedback given to learners, feedback *from* the learners during and after a training session is crucial, and is a key element for the evaluation of those sessions as there is continuous evaluation of the activity for its optimal outcomes. Every part of the process is commented through a platform, these data are collected, evaluated for the optimisation of the training process. Therefore a forum will be created in OpenPlato where participants will be able to upload comments at any time and a survey at the end of the training process will be distributed among them for the assessment of the training. In addition, specific Questions & Answers will be created which will focus on collecting various doubts but also alternative ways of conducting the training, and will be available throughout the activity.

Support material

Table 2.2 presents the main types of material that will be used during the training process, which will be constantly updated for optimisation and whenever new services and tools emerge.

Table 2.2

Guides:	Building and using indicators and metrics that include OS Using services and tools according to RRA Shaping/customising the individual's profile
Use cases:	Using indicators in different stakeholders Using services and tools according to RRA by different stakeholder groups Individual's profiles of different key target groups
Video tutorials:	Produce videos for training and demonstration purposes
Factsheets:	References on RRA policies References on indicators and metrics that includes OS practices References on GraspOS services and tools
FAQs:	Answers to the provided services and tools
Webinars and Community Calls:	Include various presentations of the participants regarding RRA, indicators and metrics in OS and recordings of the calls